

Beyond the Storage Wall: Bounded Self-Authenticating Validator State for Authenticated Ledgers at Machine Scale

Title page

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Files in this submission.

- *Title page* (this document): non-anonymous, for editor use only.
- *Main manuscript*, 25 pages, anonymised, `acmart acmsmall`.
- *Online supplementary material*, 15 pages, anonymised.
- *Cover letter*, addressed to the Editor-in-Chief.

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